

New Hydroxamic Acid Derivatives as Spectrophotometric Reagents for Vanadium(V): Rapid Determination of Vanadium in Ilmenite

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N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine, its halogen and methyl substituted derivatives and N-p-nitrobenzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine are synthesised and applied for spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V). In strong hydrochloric acid solutions vanadium(V) forms 1:2 complexes with these reagents which on extraction into chloroform show maximum absorption at 530 nm at which the sensitivities are about 0.01 μg of vanadium per cm^2 . Of the prepared reagents, N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine is used for the spectrophotometric determination of traces of vanadium(V) present in ilmenite, after oxidizing vanadium to vanadium(V) with potassium iodate and masking titanium(IV) with fluoride.

Earlier, N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine was introduced as a very selective reagent for titanium(IV)¹ and niobium(V)². Attempts for improving the selectivity of the reagent by introducing suitable substituents resulted in the introduction of seven new spectrophotometric reagents for vanadium(V). The procedure developed for the direct determination of vanadium in ilmenite seems to be superior to almost all other methods developed for the purpose.

Experimental

Preparation of reagents: The reagents were synthesised by the condensation of acetylsalicyloyl chloride and phenylhydroxylamine or its methyl or halogen substituted derivatives in presence of sodium hydrogen carbonate as described in a previous publication¹. Similarly N-p-nitrobenzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine was prepared from p-nitrobenzoyl chloride and phenylhydroxylamine. The m.p. and elemental analyses results are given in Table 1.

General procedure: An aliquot of vanadate solution (prepared from AR ammonium vanadate and standardised) containing vanadium in the optimum concentration range was taken in a separatory funnel and added enough 10 M hydrochloric acid so as to make acid strength in the range 5-8 M. Added 5 ml of 0.25% reagent solution in chloroform and 5 ml of pure chloroform. Shaken gently for about two minutes and transferred the pink chloroform layer to a 25 ml volumetric flask after drying the extract with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Extraction was repeated with 5 ml more chloroform and collected in the same flask. The volume of the extract was made upto the mark and absorbance measured at 530 nm against chloroform blank.

Procedure for ilmenite: A suitable aliquot of ilmenite solution was taken in a separatory funnel and added 1 ml of 10% potassium iodate after acidifying to 6-8 N using 18 N sulfuric acid. Titanium was masked with 5 ml of 20% sodium fluoride and extracted vanadium(V) as described earlier. The chloroform extract was again shaken with 5-8 M hydrochloric acid for enhancing the sensitivity. The results of the determination are given in Table 3.

Discussion

Absorption spectra: All the complexes are violet in colour and have absorption maximum at 530 nm. The reagents are not found to absorb at this wavelength.

Sensitivity, molar extinction coefficient, etc.: The sensitivities of the methods as defined by Sandell³ are about 0.01 μg of vanadium/ cm^2 . The molar extinction coefficient, relative photometric error⁴, optimum concentration range⁵ etc. are given in Table 2.

The optimum amount of reagent and acid strength are also given in Table 2.

Composition of the complexes: The compositions of the complexes formed by vanadium and the various reagents were established by the application of Job's method⁶ of continuous variations, the molar ratio⁷ and slope ratio⁸ methods. For Job's method and molar ratio method, equimolar solutions (0.001 M) of vanadium and the reagent were used. In Job's method, a total volume of 10 ml of complimentary mixtures containing vanadium and the reagents in chloroform were shaken and the organic layer was diluted to 25 ml. In molar ratio method 2 ml of vanadium solution was extracted with varying

TABLE 1. NEW HYDROXAMIC ACIDS

No.	Reagent	M.P. °C	Formula	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen	
				Found	Required	Found	Required	Found	Required
I.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine	128	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	66.89	66.42	4.76	4.79	5.06	5.16
II.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-o-tolylhydroxylamine	146	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N	68.37	67.37	5.92	5.26	5.21	4.91
III.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-m-tolylhydroxylamine	127	„	68.32	67.37	5.18	5.26	5.39	4.91
IV.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-p-tolylhydroxylamine	154	„	68.25	67.37	5.13	5.26	5.50	4.91
V.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-o-chlorophenylhydroxylamine	144	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄ NCl	59.43	58.92	3.53	3.93	4.81	4.58
VI.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-m-chlorophenylhydroxylamine	94	„	59.20	58.92	3.80	3.93	5.02	4.58
VII.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine	147	„	59.82	58.92	4.29	3.93	5.05	4.58
VIII.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-o-bromophenylhydroxylamine	129	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄ NBr	52.80	51.44	3.50	3.43	4.16	4.00
IX.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-o-iodophenylhydroxylamine	145	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄ NI	46.39	45.35	3.20	3.02	4.00	3.53
X.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-p-iodophenylhydroxylamine	120	„	45.90	45.35	3.00	3.02	3.50	3.53
XI.	N-p-nitrobenzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine	158	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂	60.52	60.47	4.02	3.88	10.57	10.85

TABLE 2. REAGENTS USED FOR VANADIUM DETERMINATIONS

No.	Reagent	Optimum HCl strength <i>M</i>	Vol. of 0.25% (w/v) reagent solution ml	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ at 530 $m\mu$	Optimum concentration range $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$	Percentage relative analytical error	Molar absorptivity
I.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine	4-8	2.0	0.011	1.5-9.5	2.17	4400
IV.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-p-tolylhydroxylamine	5-8	2.0	0.011	1.5-9.5	1.54	4170
V.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-o-chlorophenylhydroxylamine	4.5-8	1.5	0.011	2-10	1.37	4170
VII.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine	4-8	1.5	0.011	1.5-9.5	1.53	4400
VIII.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-o-bromophenylhydroxylamine	3.5-8	2.0	0.010	1.0-9	1.73	4630
X.	N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-p-iodophenylhydroxylamine	4-8	2.0	0.013	2-10	1.41	3704
XI.	N-p-nitrobenzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine	5-8	2.0	0.010	1.5-9	1.28	4750

TABLE 3. DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN ILMENITE

	Experiment			Mean %
	1	2	3	
% Vanadium found	0.053	0.055	0.050	0.0526

volumes of reagent solution and measured the absorbances after dilution of the extract to 25 ml with chloroform. The molar ratio curves as well as the slope ratio curves proved the formation of 1 : 2 complexes with respect to vanadium and the reagent.

Effect of diverse ions : In the absorbance measurements of the violet vanadium chelates in chloroform medium, foreign ions like Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II), Mg(II), Mn(II), Cu(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Zn(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Sb(III), As(III), Bi(III), La(III),

Th(IV), U(VI), iodide, fluoride, tartrate, oxalate, citrate, borate, acetate, phosphate, and EDTA did not interfere even upto 1000 times excess. Iodate interfered in the presence of hydrochloric acid but not in the presence of sulphuric acid. Co(IV) and Zr(IV) were masked by EDTA and Ti(IV) and Nb(V) using fluoride. But W(VI) and Mo(VI) interfered. Reducing agents like Fe(II) and hydroxylamine and strong oxidising agents like permanganate, dichromate and nitric acid should be avoided.

The interference of Mo(VI) in 100-fold excess could be eliminated by reducing the vanadate with 0.5 g of sodium sulphite and then extracting Mo(VI) several times with reagent solution in chloroform. Vanadium in the aqueous layer was oxidised with excess of potassium iodate.

Reagent properties : All the reagents studied are structurally similar to N-benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine. The introduction of various substituent

groups in the benzene nuclei of these reagents resulted in varying chelating tendencies. Thus, N-acetylsalicyloyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine forms complexes with only a few cations compared to N-benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine which may be attributed to steric factors caused by the fairly large acetoxy group at the ortho position with respect to the coordinating carbonyl group.

Altogether eleven reagents were synthesised. All of these are new compounds except N-*p*-nitrobenzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine which was earlier synthesised⁹. Out of these, seven reagents could be applied for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium. The colour reaction with the other reagents were either too insensitive or unstable for spectrophotometric study.

The *o*-tolyl derivative (II) does not form any coloured complex with vanadium. In this, the electron repelling character of the methyl group has a dominating effect over any steric hindrance since the similar *o*-chloro derivative (V) forms complex fairly well, even though chlorine is larger in size than methyl group. The halogen possesses electron repelling conjugative effect as well as electron attracting character, of which the latter effect is found to favour chelation. The size of bromine also is not sufficient to hinder the entry of the metal ion as shown by the fact that the *o*-bromo derivative (VIII) reacts well with vanadium. But in the case of iodine, the size is sufficient to hinder the uptake of the metal ion at its vicinity so that the *o*-iodo

compound (IX) is not forming any stable complex with vanadium. But when the iodine is far away from the coordination centre, complexation takes place readily as is found with reagent (X).

The meta substituted derivatives are found to be inert in their reactions with metal ions. No satisfactory reason can be attributed to this. The increased sensitivity of N-*p*-nitrobenzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine is due to the bathochromic effect of the nitro group.

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